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1 M3.2 - Proposal for an EOSC PID Service providers coordination mechanism¹

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¹ The original milestone title *MS3.2 EOSC PID providers coordination mechanism proposed* has been updated to be more clear to the external reader.

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2 Versioning and contribution history

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number
ISNI	International Standard Name Identifier
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
ROR	Research Organization Registry
PID	Persistent identifier
SP	Service Provider
RAiD	Research Activity Identifier
SRIA	EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SWHID	Software Heritage identifier
URN	Uniform Resource Name
URN:NBN	National Bibliographical Number
WP	Work Package
WG	Working Group

4 Introduction

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are crucial to enable and achieve the FAIR principles, which describe how research data and other entities within the research lifecycle should be made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Some of the goals of the FAIR-IMPACT project are related to working with PID service providers and infrastructures to better understand and meet user needs, align with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) PID policy, and maximize PID adoption. In the context of the project, these goals are addressed under a specific Work Package (WP) dedicated to PIDs. To achieve these goals, more coordination between PID service providers and EOSC is needed, resulting in PIDs for diverse research outputs including publications, data, software, instruments, services, people, and organisations. After establishing a joint value proposition by PID providers ([Milestone 3.1 Joint value proposition by relevant PID providers](#)), the next step is a proposal for a mechanism to support the necessary coordination. This report outlines the proposed coordination mechanism.

5 Description of the Milestone

This report describes the achievement of milestone M3.2 *EOSC PID providers coordination mechanism proposed* in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT project. It describes the role of the coordination mechanism, the processes for its creation, as well as verification measures linked to this achievement.

5.1 Role of the milestone

The proposal of a coordination mechanism for PID providers is a critical milestone for the FAIR-IMPACT project and the second step towards achieving a shared-long term vision for PID service providers in EOSC (Deliverable 3.1 to be achieved in month 34 of the project).

Figure 1. FAIR-IMPACT milestones to achieve a shared long-term vision for PID service providers in EOSC

5.1.1 Means of verification

The means of verification for achieving this Milestone are:

1. Discussions with task members during monthly calls
2. MS3.2 brainstorming session
3. [Input from PID providers](#) as part of MS3.1²

² Mejias, Gabriela, Cousijn, Helena, Marjamaa-Mankinen, Liisa, van Lieshout, Natascha, Tatum, Clifford, & Lambert, Simon. (2023). M3.1 - Joint value proposition by relevant PID providers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798215>

6 Proposal of the coordination mechanism

6.1 Introduction

The FAIR-IMPACT project aims to promote and expand the FAIR principles in research within Europe. PIDs and their associated metadata are a critical component to enable the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of research entities (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and supporting a more coordinated approach to their creation and use is a key aim for our project. To this end, one of the key goals of FAIR-IMPACT involves establishing strong links between EOSC and PID providers, in order to drive and amplify the implementation of the FAIR principles in Europe.

6.2 The need for a coordination mechanism

EOSC ultimately aims to develop a Web of FAIR Data and services for science in Europe upon which a wide range of value-added services can be built. These range from visualisation and analytics to long-term information preservation and the monitoring of the uptake of open science practices.

Currently, the development of EOSC is in the second phase (2021-2027) and participation of all stakeholders is needed to gain the full potential. The full deployment of EOSC is expected to lead to higher research productivity, new insights and innovations, as well as improved reproducibility and trust in science.

Effective coordination between EOSC and PID providers is crucial for the following reasons:

- According to EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap 2025 and 2026-2027³ (in consultation phase)
 - Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are a critical component of the underlying infrastructure to allow resources to be accurately identified, accessed and linked to other objects.
 - Many types of PIDs are already in common usage and this should be sustained via support at the European and national levels, in particular encouraging adoption by communities that are not already active. The integration of different actors supporting PID services should also be coordinated at European level for sustainability. Support should be directed towards national and institutional services, enabling the adoption of PIDs to

³ https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/MAR_2025-27_draft.pdf

ensure content federated into EOSC is well contextualised. Another important aspect to increase adoption is to raise awareness among researchers on the benefits of PIDs.

- Data and metadata services being supported at the European level such as the PID Meta-Resolver, Data Type Registries, PID graph technologies and the FAIRCORE4EOSC PID Compliance Assessment Toolkit should be promoted by Member States and institutions to promote uptake and researchers should be encouraged to use PIDs for the whole research lifecycle. Best practices for PID adoption and interoperability should also be promoted.
- A long-term sustainability plan should also be developed within EOSC for PIDs to help the research community understand their long term financial commitment related with PID adoption.
- Numerous technologies, databases and cloud systems use local identifiers. To create a functioning PID ecosystem for the EOSC and to implement the FAIR principles, PID services should be interoperable with each other and between PID service providers, as well as across research infrastructures. The EOSC PID Policy seeks to accommodate mature and established PID practices, schemes, technologies and providers which have a global presence. Improving research data and outputs Findability, Accessibility and Reusability. One of EOSC's primary ambitions⁴ is to provide an “open multi-disciplinary environment where [researchers] can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes”. PIDs offer a standardized mechanism for identifying, referencing and accessing research data and outputs stored across diverse systems and platforms, streamlining the research discovery process for researchers, innovators, educators and beyond. By harmonizing the efforts of EOSC and PIDs providers, research accessibility can be significantly increased, promoting cross-disciplinary collaboration and knowledge dissemination.
- **Enabling Interoperability:** Interoperability is a cornerstone of the FAIR principles, and integrating PIDs within the EOSC ecosystem can ensure that research outputs are not only discoverable and accessible but also seamlessly interoperable across systems, platforms and infrastructures. This interconnection can foster a more robust research ecosystem. For these reasons, coordination between EOSC and PID providers can contribute to achieving this goal.

⁴ <https://eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc>

6.3 Requirements for effective coordination

In order to provide existing PIDs through EOSC, to onboard established PID providers into EOSC, and to enable a strong collaboration between EOSC and PID Service Providers, an effective coordination mechanism is required. The following topics/ issues should be addressed:

- 1. Co-operation between PID Service Providers and EOSC:** In order to provide existing PIDs and onboarding established PIDs through EOSC, it is crucial to establish a communication channel to align both PID providers and EOSC efforts, ensuring that the identification of different entities is carried out in a consistent way across EOSC infrastructure and that the community understands how to adopt these PIDs.
- 2. Emerging PIDs:** Encouraging the use of mature and established PIDs that are globally recognised supports short to mid-term interoperability. However, it is essential that emerging PIDs can be identified and incorporated into the EOSC ecosystem for EOSC to remain a fully functioning and comprehensive environment for diverse research outputs and PIDs as/if required by the community. As such, a coordination mechanism should include some means of horizon scanning.
- 3. Ensuring EOSC Compliance by PID Service Providers:** should there be changes to the EOSC PID Policy or if new policies and/or requirements emerge, PID service providers should be informed to ensure both timely feedback and compliance. To this end, a coordination mechanism should enable the sharing of draft policies and a means of providing feedback. It's worth noting that the FAIRCORE4EOSC project,⁵ in cooperation with FAIR-IMPACT, is currently developing a Compliance Assessment Toolkit⁶ to measure EOSC PID Policy compliance. Once the projects are complete, a community mechanism will be important for maintenance of the tool.
- 4. Channeling needs across the EOSC community:** an effective coordination mechanism would help identify challenges and needs within the EOSC community and share those with the PID Service Providers.

⁵ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

⁶ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

5. Sharing outputs from relevant projects⁷: several EOSC-related projects, such as FAIR-IMPACT and its Synchronisation Force,⁸ FAIRCORE4EOSC, etc. contribute to the development of EOSC in relation to PIDs. Sharing these outputs could ensure that innovations are effectively implemented and aligned with the overarching objectives of both EOSC and PID Service Providers.

6.4 Stakeholders for effective coordination

EOSC is a dynamic ecosystem with actively evolving policies, technologies, and funding mechanisms. Coordinating the communication of any relevant updates with PID providers can ensure that both remain informed and aligned. The above-mentioned Communication channels could be established to share information on policy changes, funding opportunities, and technological advancements to keep all stakeholders well-informed. To streamline synergies, we would propose that the EOSC PID Policy and Implementation Task Force⁹ could take the lead in this initiative. This group is already established and supported by the EOSC Association and includes a wide range of PID related stakeholders, including PID service providers.

To ensure the effective establishment and operation of a coordination mechanism between EOSC and PID providers, a wide range of stakeholders should be involved¹⁰. These stakeholders could contribute their expertise and perspectives to shape a robust, inclusive and sustainable coordination mechanism. The following stakeholders should be represented:

- 1. European Commission:** Communication with the EC can ensure that the coordination mechanism aligns with broader European strategies, policies, and funding.
- 2. EOSC Association:** Communication with the EOSC Association can ensure that the coordination mechanism aligns with broader European strategies, policies, and funding.
- 3. PID Providers:** engaging both established and new PID providers is essential for the success of the coordination mechanism. The coordination mechanism should include all PID providers that have been onboarded into the EOSC Portal and providers of established PIDs

⁷ Kalaitzi, Vasso, Dillo, Ingrid, Turner, Daniel, Ashley, Kevin, Davidson, Joy, Nordling, Josefine, Parland-von Essen, Jessica, Jonquet, Clement, Aubin, Sophie, Priddy, Mike, Verburg, Maaïke, Fink, Anne Sofie, Rouchon, Olivier, Pittonet, Sara, Mari, Marialetizia, & Meneses, Rita. (2023). EOSC Policy Brief for FAIR-IMPACT. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8255645>

⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/synchronisation-force>

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/pid-policy-implementation>

¹⁰ de Castro, Pablo, Herb, Ulrich, Rothfritz, Laura, & Schöpfel, Joachim. (2023). Building the plane as we fly it: the promise of Persistent Identifiers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7258286>

such as Crossref, DataCite, IGSN, ISNI, ISSN, ORCID, ROR, RAiD, SWHIDs, URN, URN:MNM to continue the work already started by this task.

4. Research Policymakers and Funding Bodies (e.g. national research councils): National and regional research policymakers and funders have a strong influence and impact on research practices. Involving these stakeholders in the coordination mechanism would improve alignment of EOSC and PID providers efforts with national research priorities.

5. ESRIs and Data Spaces: Research Infrastructures and Data Spaces,¹¹ which are discipline specific and include data repositories, archives, tools and standards, are key components of the research landscape. They not only provide specific PID services but also general and cross cutting services. Involving infrastructure and data space representatives is essential to ensure that the coordination mechanism addresses and enhances data interoperability and reusability, and that adoption pathways are feasible and desirable.

6. Relevant Research Data Alliance (RDA) Groups: The RDA promotes collaboration and provides standards for research data management. Engaging relevant RDA groups within the coordination mechanism could ensure that the best practices and standards advocated by RDA are integrated into the EOSC-PID framework, promoting further data interoperability and discoverability. For example, one relevant group is Persistent Identification of Instruments WG¹², where one of the FAIR-IMPACT partners UKRI-STFC participates.

6.5 Coordination Mechanism between EOSC and PID Providers

To achieve effective coordination between the European Open Science Cloud and PID providers, a well-defined, flexible and sustainable coordination mechanism is needed. We propose that this coordination is led by the EOSC Association leveraging existing mechanisms such as the EOSC PID Policy & Implementation Task Force, bringing all stakeholders mentioned above into the task force. This is a proposal of how the coordination mechanism should function.

A coordination mechanism between the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and PID Providers should embody certain characteristics to operate effectively. These include transparency and open communication, flexibility to adapt to the evolving research landscape. Additionally, the mechanism should ensure knowledge sharing and accountability. By encompassing these characteristics, the mechanism can facilitate collaboration, advance open research, and promote FAIRness within the European research community.

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/persistent-identification-instruments-wg>

It is focused on supporting a shared understanding, increased awareness, effective collaboration, and enhanced transparency between key stakeholders:

1. Raising Awareness of EOSC: the coordination mechanism should actively disseminate information about EOSC's role and its policies and recommendations (e.g., the PID policy and related PID framework). Agreed and regular communication channels, such as virtual meetings and newsletters can help ensure that stakeholders are well-informed and up-to-date.

2. Improving shared understanding among PID Providers: the coordination mechanism should facilitate an open dialogue to ensure that the EOSC community and related stakeholders can better understand how PID providers function. The FREYA project delivered many outputs¹³ and these resources should be reused as the foundational groundwork to understand the PID landscape, PID architecture and complementary technologies like the PID Graph among other relevant topics.

Some potential risks in the establishment of a coordination mechanism include duplication of effort, parallel conversations, lack of urgency and unclear value proposition¹⁴ to participate in such a group. To keep the coordination mechanism as concrete and focused as possible, the goal should be clear: to agree on and establish an official and unique communication channel between EOSC and PID providers in order to raise awareness and improve understanding of both EOSC and PID providers' ongoing work and new initiatives. We propose the following communication channels:

1. **PID-Forum¹⁵ dedicated channel:** where all the stakeholders outlined in section 6.4 can share information and updates, raise questions and exchange on a more frequent basis.
2. **Regular newsletter:** where relevant overarching information such as new technical and governance developments, events, funding opportunities and more can be shared on a regular basis (frequency to be determined).
3. **Periodical (e.g. bi-annual) virtual meetings:** where selected stakeholders can engage each other and exchange ideas based on a predefined agenda established from the

¹³ <https://www.project-freya.eu/en/resources/project-output>

¹⁴ A joint value proposition from PID providers to EOSC has already been established on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798215> and this work should be expanded as part of FAIR-IMPACT D3.1

¹⁵ [The PID Forum](#) is a global information and discussion platform for persistent identifiers (PIDs), which brings together the various communities working with PIDs in the research world. It's a virtual place for sharing best practices, announcing events, asking questions, and having discussions about PIDs. The PID Forum was initiated by the FREYA project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 777523. From January 2021 it is hosted by NISO, the National Information Standards Organization.

two channels mentioned above. These could also take place as part of the FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force workshops, EOSC Symposiums and other community events.

7 Conclusions and next steps

A strong and fruitful collaboration between EOSC and PID Service Providers requires an effective coordination mechanism to improve adoption and address current and potential needs and challenges. The present report is a first proposal of the scope of such a coordination mechanism. Here, we propose that this coordination is led by the EOSC Association leveraging existing mechanisms such as the EOSC PID Policy & Implementation Task Force, and would be expanded to include all the relevant stakeholders needed for effective coordination. Relevant communication channels will be established to ensure bidirectional communication so PID providers are aware of EOSC policies, while EOSC stakeholders are aware of PID provider offerings and requirements. As next steps, we plan to align requirements for onboarding PID providers into EOSC, including emerging PIDs (M3.3) and circulate a survey among PID providers to gather feedback on their needs and expectations around effective communication and coordination with EOSC.

8 References

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<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

